

REALITIES IN THE TRANSLATION

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Abstract: The article reveals the difficulties and problems that arise in translating the realities of the works of Uzbek literature into a foreign language and emphasizes the issues of solving these difficulties in different ways.

Key words: realities, transliteration, national-historical color, national reality, national characters

In the history of Uzbek literature of the 20th century, the prose works of the academic writer Oibek have a special place. His novel "Navoi" is important in this regard. It depicts the brilliant work of Alisher Navoi, a thinker poet who lived and created in Herat during the extremely difficult period of the 15th century. In the novel, the lives of historical figures, the scenes of the historical period are illuminated in bright artistic pictures. In fact, the reality of national life, national characters, national color is illuminated through the words and realities of a particular nation. Realities are a complex and complex category of the lexical system of the language. They are one of the concepts that express the national color. The realema, which are the names of special concepts and events related to the life, culture, and history of each nation, includes a part of the way of life of that nation. This is the peculiar complexity of realities. Before translating them, the translator studies the concept related to this reality, compares the translation with the language, and looks for a suitable equivalent in the language dictionary. The most important thing is to understand this reality. Because, if the concept is misinterpreted, not only the translation will change, but also the relevant national landscape, the piece of culture related to this reality will be delivered to the reader of a foreign language.

Issues related to reality and their translation have been studied in the works of many scientists. Among the world scientists, L.S. Barkhudarov, A.D. Schweizer, Ye.M. Vereshagin, V.G. Kostomarov, L.N. Sobolev, V.S. Vinogradov, S. Vlahov, S. Florin, V.N. Komissarov, L.K. Latishev, I.S. Alekseeva, T.A. Kazakova, G.D. Tomakhin, M. In the scientific works of Lederer, A. Yu. Kuznesov, and M. T. Bagoyeva, it is possible to find solutions to many problems related to the translation of realities, but the translation of each reality is individual. They do not repeat each other, they cannot use the same translation method. M.T. Baqoeva says about the expression of national colors and realities in translation: "Regardless of the genre, theme, idea of the works, the process of their translation is different from each other. In the theoretical and scientific works of Uzbek linguists G. Salomov, K. Musayev, R. Shirinova, D. Djumanova, R. Kasimova, M. Barotova, special attention is paid to the problems related to the translation of realities. For example, while thinking about Uzbek realities, D. Djumanova classifies them into eleven groups.

Russian scientist V.S. Vinogradov offers four different translation methods for translating realities. M. Nadjimkhodjayev transliterated and transcribed them; create a neologism; translate realities with reality; explain; distinguishes types of substitution with alternatives. Transcription and transliteration of realities in translation studies in general; descriptive translation; hyponymic translation; simile translation; types such as kalka translation are shown, and we, relying on these translation methods, try to justify the reflection of the national color in the novel based on the comparison of the original and the translation of the novel. Based on D. Djumanova's classification, we will consider our examples in certain groups.

The appearance of the name of household items as a reality.

a) name of food and drink. Uzbek part: *Besh-olti yoshda maktabidan ozod bo'lib yugurib kelarkan, u darrov bag'riga bosar, sut, patir non va shirinliklar berar edi*, in English: *When Alisher would come back from school after his lessons she would hug him and give him bread, milk and sweets when he was five or six*

years old. The reality of *patir non* presented in the passage is turned into *bread*. But *patir non* is a type of bread that is cooked with oil for dear people, with special relationships, at wedding ceremonies, and the writer wanted to express how valuable Alisher Navoi's humanity is. Taking this into account, using the descriptive translation method, it is appropriate to give *patir non* in the form of puff pastry *bread*. However, it should be noted that this translation cannot fully express the concept of *patir non*, because it is a reality.

Birozdan keyin shoir halvofurush tandurdan yangi uzilgan ikkita non va juda nafis ishlangan guldor mis laganchada kesma halvo olib chiqdi the sentence is very strange and incompletely translated. It seems that the elegance of the content of the work is a little lost: *After a while a poet came to the room with fresh bread and candies*. According to the writer's description of the environment and people of that time, all professions and common people were interested in poetry and art. In this passage, the *poet* is also a pseudonym used to glorify the writing of poetry by this *halvaforush*. So, not just a poet in the translation, but a *poet-halvah seller* using the transcription method fully expresses the content. Also, in the sentence, the realities of *tandoor* and *copper plate* are left out. The concept of *tandoor* came to the British through the culture of the Indian people. Therefore, if this term is given with the word *tandoori*, the same concept is understood. *Mis lagancha* can be given in the form of a *cooper plate* using a descriptive translation: *After a while halvah seller-poet came into the room with 2 fresh loaves of tandoori bread and sliced halva on a delicate inwrought cooper plate*.

It is known that the novel "Navoi" is a historical work, and most of the work consists of outdated or historical words. Understanding some of his words is difficult even for an Uzbek reader: *bork*, *chorpakhil*, etc. A reader of a foreign language needs help in understanding such words during the reading process and thereby understanding a historical event or an event occurring in a certain era and society, for example, a portrait of a hero. Therefore, giving an explanation of obsolete words or realities is one of the necessary conditions of translation.

In conclusion, it can be said that realias are national words that express only the unique features and aspects of each nation. The main methods used in their translation are transcription and transliteration, the methods of giving reality by reality, which are conveyed to the representative of the second language through interpretation. Then the reader will have a general, integrated concept of this concept. In some places, it is more beneficial to use the equivalent of realism in a second language, because if the reader reads with familiar words, the reading process becomes easier and the interest in the work and the development of events increases.

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